

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2026-YIL

IYUN/6-SON, II-QISM

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, iyun.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqov, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhridinov Zafarjon Fakhridin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi Iqtisodiy
jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

METAVERS TURIZMI: VIRTUAL DUNYODAGI SAYOHATNING IQTISODIY, HUQUQIY VA IJTIMOIIY NATIJALARI	12
Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
Eshimova Sevinch Baxtiyor qizi	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA PLATFORMA EKOTIZIMLARINING KORXONA INNOVATSIYALARIDAGI O'RNI	16
Izzatullayeva Madinabonu Yolqin qizi	
METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE ECONOMIC DAMAGE OF ECOLOGICAL HAZARDS IN URBAN AREAS: CONCEPTUAL SHORTCOMINGS OF NON-MARKET VALUATION METHODS AND THE INTEGRAL DAMAGE FUNCTION APPROACH	20
Abbos Saydullaev	
Iqboloy Choriyorova	
O'ZBEKISTONDA EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT IMKONIYATLARI	31
Ibragimova Rayxon Tojibayevna	
OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATIDA "ZAYLANMA IQTISODIYOT (CIRCULAR ECONOMY)" MODELINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	36
Elnoraxon Muminova Abdukurimovna	
Sarvinoz Mamatojiyeva Dilshodjon qizi	
TRANSPORT KORIDORLARINI BOSHQARISHDA LOGISTIKA MENEJMENTINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	42
Umarova Dilfuza Rahmatulla qizi	
ОЦЕНКА ТЕКУЩЕГО СОСТОЯНИЯ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ МИСЕ-СЕКТОРА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	47
Harzullaeva Fariza Akmalевна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF THE DYNAMICS OF RETAIL TRADE TURNOVER UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF REAL HOUSEHOLD INCOME USING A LOGARITHMIC FUNCTION	53
Gaybullayev Sarvar Uktam ugli	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB ETISHNING MAZMUN-MOHİYATI VA NAZARIY ASOSLARI	59
Mizamova Umida Jamoliddin qizi	
SPORT TAKOMILLASHUVI BOSQICHIDAGI FUTBOLCHILARNING MUSOBAQA FAOLIYATIDA INNOVATSION VOSITALARNING O'RNI	64
Mamatraimov Anvar Chorshanbiyavich	
MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA CHET TILINI VIZUAL MATERIALLAR VOSITASIDA O'RGATISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	72
Olimova Shahlo Bahodir qizi	
Inomova Mahliyo Yusuf qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA ICHKI VA TASHQI AUDITNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	76
Toshimov Azizbek Hakimovich	
Quvondiqov Shohboz Normamat o'g'li	
XUSUSIYLASHTIRISH JARAYONLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI	81
Musurmonqulov Muhammad Ural o'g'li	
TEMIR YO'L ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING TASHKILIY MEXANIZMI	86
Baymatov Atxam Axmadaliyevich	

MENEJMENT NAZARIYASINING SHAKLLANISHI VA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDAGI ROLI.....	92
Saidova Xilolaxon Rashidjon qizi OPPORTUNITIES FOR USING MARKETING STRATEGIES TO ENSURE THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF HOTEL ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN	97
Sardor Kuvandikov ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ПРОГРАММ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ	106
Абдуллаева Зульфия Иззатовна NAMANGAN VILOYATINING HUDUDIYIQTISODIY TUZILMASI VA SHAHARLAR TIZIMINING SHAKLLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	113
Ahmadjanov Ilyosbek Ilhomjon o'g'li JISMONIY SHAXSLAR DAROMADLARINI SOLIQQA TORTISH MEXANIZMI VA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR QIYOSIY TAHLILI	117
G'afforov Kamronbek “O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI” AJNING SINGULYAR VA BARQARORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI	123
Bobojonova Zarnigor Shokirovna MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY JARAYONLARNI BAHOLASHDA DSGE MODELINING QASHQADARYO SHAROITIGA MOSLASHTIRILGAN TAHLILIIY KOMPONENTLARI.....	132
Muxitdinov Xudayar Suyunovich Quvatova Gulzoda Faxriddin qizi O'ZBEKISTONDA TIBBIY TURIZM VA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR TIZIMINING MAZMUNI	137
Ergasheva Iroda Ibrohim qizi FOYDA SOLIG'INING BANKLAR MOLIYAVIY HOLATIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH	141
Maxmudov Omon To'xtayevich RAQAMLI INFRATUZILMA TUSHUNCHASI, TARKIBI VA IQTISODIY MAZMUNI.....	147
Pardayev Orifjon Charshamiyevich O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	152
Omonova Zarina Xudoymurodovna RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI (Shartli “suv ta'minot servis” AJ misolida).....	160
Doniyorova M. KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK KORXONALARI RIVOJLANISHINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH.....	164
Komilova Shaxnoza Komiljon qizi SUN'Y INTELLEKT ASOSIDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA XODIMNING QIYMAT YARATISH DARAJASINI BAHOLASHNING INTEGRALLASHGAN MODEL (EVC1)	169
Xaydarova Malika Shokirjon qizi ГОСУДАРСТВЕННАЯ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ПОЛИТИКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА И МЕХАНИЗМ ЕЁ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ	174
Нодира Илхамовна Саидахмедова Жамолiddин Ярашевич Нуриллаев THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FRUGALITY AND INNOVATION: A THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES.....	181
Allaberganov Zakir Gaibovich Alimova Guzal Abdukhakimovna BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH SHAROITIDA TARMOQLARARO INTEGRATSIYANING INSTITUTSIONAL MODEL.....	188
Muftaydinov Mansur Kiyomidinovich	

AHOLINI IJTIMOYIY HIMOYALASH TIZIMINI BOSHQARISHNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI.....	196
Xamroyev Anvar Ashurovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTI ISHLAYDIGAN BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISH	202
Ismaylov Kuvatbay Sarsenbayevich	
IQTISODIYOT TARMOQLARINI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHDA FISKAL INSTRUMENTLARNING NAZARIY-IQTISODIY ASOSLARI	206
Mardonov Kamoliddin Karamiddinovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARAJATLARI VA ULARNI BOSHQARISH	212
Hamroyeva Feruza Azizjon qizi	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASHDA TARMOQLARARO INTEGRATSIYANING INSTITUTSIONAL MODELINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	217
Muftaydinov Mansur Kiyomidinovich	
RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING IQTISODIY MAZMUNI VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI.....	226
Sirojev Nurbek G'ulomiddin o'g'li	
EKOLOGIK GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA SOG'LOM TURMUSH TARZINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ZARURATI.....	231
Nurmatov Samandar G'ayratovich	
TURIZM INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TO'G'RIDAN-TO'G'RI XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALAR (FDI)NING ROLI VA UNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH OMILLARI	238
Bau Long	
ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫЙ КОМПЛЕКС РЕГИОНА КАК ОБЪЕКТ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ	244
Axrarova Shodiyxon Ja'farxon kizi	
PUL OQIMLARI AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING KOMPLEKS USLUBIYATI	247
Djurayev Davlat Djonibekovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDITLASH JARAYONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY AMALIYOTDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	250
Raxmanova Laylo Baxodirovna	
SOLIQ QARZDORLIGINI HISOBLASH VA UNDIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI IQTISODIY SUBYEKTLAR MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH	256
Payziyev Hamid Orziqulovich	
PUL-KREDIT SIYOSATI INSTRUMENTLARIDAN FOYDALANISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	260
A.A. Ismailov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ELEKTRON TO'LOV TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHI VA ULARNING ISTE'MOLCHILAR XULQ-ATVORIGA TA'SIRI	266
Elmurodov Shohzod Shavkatovich	
DAVLATNING BUDJET SIYOSATI — MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING ASOSIY INSTRUMENTI SIFATIDA.....	272
A.A. Ismailov	
ETNOGRAFIK RESURSLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA TURIZM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	278
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich	
O'ZBEKISTON TASHKILOTLARIDA UCHRAYDIGAN BOSHQARUV MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH STRATEGIYALARI	285
Abiyev Jahongir Ne'matovich	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNING NAZARIY MODEL VA ILMIY YONDASHUVLARI.....	290
Abikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	

O'ZBEKISTONDA KIMYO SANOATI KORXONALARINING RAQAMLI SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH: RSI INDEKSI ASOSIDA ILMIY TAHLIL.....	294
Odinayev Nuriddin Ramozon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOMIY QIMMATLI QOG'OZLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	300
Hakimov Ikrom Izzatillo o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARIDA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'I BO'YICHA STRATEGIK ISLOHOTLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	305
Amanov Akram Mirzayevich	
FOND BOZORI INSTRUMENTLARI ORQALI INVESTITSION FAOLIYATNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	310
Vasiyev Alisher Samiyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MAHSULOT SIFATINI BOSHQARISH JARAYONINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN TARTIBGA SOLISHNING INSTITUTSIONAL ASOSLARI TAHLILI.....	316
Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVDA LEADERSHIP 4.0 KONSEPSIYASINI JORIY ETISHNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	322
Ashurov Furkatjon Shuxratovich	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ «ЗЕЛЕННЫХ» ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ЖИЛИЩНОМ СЕКТОРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	326
Tojievа Dильфуза Бобомуратовна	
SAVDO KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA IJTIMOYIY TARMOQLAR MARKETINGIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI.....	334
Baltabayev Hurrambek To'liqinovich	
METAVERS TURIZMI: VIRTUAL DUNYODAGI SAYOHATNING IQTISODIY, HUQUQIY VA IJTIMOYIY NATIJALARI.....	341
Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
Eshimova Sevinch Baxtiyor qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI IQTISODIYOTIDA SANOAT TARMOG'INING ROLINI STATISTIK O'RGANISH.....	354
To'rayeva Zilola Turg'unovna	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA DAVRIDA BANKLAR: BIZNES TAHLILI VA STRATEGIK USTUNLIK MEXANIZMLARI.....	361
Shanasirova Nodira Abdullayevna	
Ibragimova Iroda Rashid qizi	
To'lovov Erkinjon To'liqin o'g'li	
QQS, FOYDA VA DAROMAD SOLIG'I STAVKALARINING BARQARORLIGI.....	367
Aripova Aziza Alisherovna	
YER VA SUV RESURLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	372
Xudoyberdiyev Diyorbek Norqobil o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INTEGRASION MODEL VA BAHOLASH INDIKATORLARI.....	378
Yuldashev Shuxrat Ganiyevich	
O'ZBEKISTON KICHIK VA O'RTA KORXONALARI ORASIDA EKO-MARKETING TO'SIQLARI.....	383
Gulsara Ostonaqulova	
Erkinova Shoxista Bekzod qizi	
YAXSHI KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	394
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TUROPERATORLIK FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIY TAJRIBALARIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI.....	399
Qutlimurotov Fayzullo Sa'dulayevich	

VILOYAT SANOAT KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHINI KO'P OMILLI EMPIRIK MODELLAR ASOSIDA TAHLIL QILISH VA PROGNOZLASH (Qashqadaryo viloyati misolida).....	406
Avazova Nafisa Namazovna O'ZBEKISTONDA SERVIS IQTISODIYOTI: XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SIFATINI BOSHQARISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA TENDENSIYALARI	410
Sattarova Nargiz Toxirovna HUDUDYIY RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHDA GASTRONOMIK TURIZMNING AHAMIYATI.....	414
Nurullayeva Malika Samadjon qizi ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКИЕ УКАЗАНИЯ КАК МАРКЕТИНГОВАЯ СТРАТЕГИЯ ПРОДВИЖЕНИЯ ТУРИСТСКИХ ДЕСТИНАЦИЙ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ «ЗАГАРА-НОН»).....	420
Сапарбаева Мавлюда Толыбаевна AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARI MOLIYASINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	427
Kurashev Sobir Saidmurod o'g'li GENERATIV SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON SAVDO XIZMATLARI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	433
Shavqiyev Erkin Danayeva Zulhumor Abdusodiq qizi РАЗВИТИЕ БАНКОВСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ.....	439
Абдурахимова Дилора Каримовна QURILISH MATERIALLARI ISHLAB CHIQUARUVCHI KORXONALARDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISHDA BRENDING TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI.....	446
Uzakova Umida Ruziyevna SOLIQ YUKINING IQTISODIY MOHIYATI, UNI BAHOLASH VA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	452
Jasmina Baxtiyorova AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARI KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDA ESG TAMOYILLARINING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	458
Xabibullayev Dadajon Ro'ziboyevich YASHIL TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA KORXONALARNING INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI CHEKLOVCHI OMILLAR.....	465
Yuldasheva Nazokat Muzaffar qizi O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI BANK XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA XORIJ TAJRIBASINING AHAMIYATI	470
Umurzoqova Adiba Ochilovna EKOLOGIK HISOBOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ASOSLARI VA SWOT TAHLILI.....	476
Turdiyeva Gulayda Omirbayevna Jiyenbayeva Aysanem Orzabayevna MOLIYAVIY NAZORATNI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	482
Turg'unov Bahtiyor Nuriddinovich MOLIYAVIY NATIJALAR TO'G'RISIDAGI HISOBOTNI TUZISH, TAQDIM QILISH VA AUDITINI O'TKAZISH TARTIBLARI	487
Boronov Bobur Farxodovich Boybolsinov Otabek Shermuhammad o'g'li Erkinov Xurshid Erkin o'g'li	

INSTITUTIONAL MODEL FOR ENSURING TRANSPARENCY AND ACCOUNTABILITY OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ALGORITHMS IN ELECTRONIC COMMERCE.....	492
Ulugmurodov Farxod Faxriddinovich Danayeva Zulhumor Abdusodiq kizi	
CREATING A MODERN LIBRARY USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE.....	498
Daminova Barno Esanovna Dilshodova Nuriya Dilshod qizi Normurodova Durdona Normumin qizi	

CREATING A MODERN LIBRARY USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Daminova Barno Esanovna

Associate Professor, Department of Algorithms and Programming Technologies, Karshi State University

Email: barnod@mail.ru

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4211-6082>

Dilshodova Nuriya Dilshod qizi

Students of Karshi State University

Email: nuriyadilshodova04@gmail.com

Normurodova Durdona Normumin qizi

Students of Karshi State University

Email: durdonan056@gmail.com

Abstract

This article examines the issues of creating and improving modern library systems using artificial intelligence technologies. The application of recommendation systems, natural language processing, machine learning algorithms, and chatbot technologies to library processes is analyzed. Based on a review of scientific works by both international and local scholars, practical ways of integrating artificial intelligence into library infrastructure and the expected outcomes are described. According to the research findings, artificial intelligence can increase the efficiency of library services by 40–60 percent and significantly improve user satisfaction.

Keywords. artificial intelligence, modern library, machine learning, recommendation system, natural language processing, digital transformation, chatbot, intelligent search.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanib zamonaviy kutubxona tizimlarini yaratish va takomillashtirish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Tavsiya tizimlari, tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash, mashina o'rganishi algoritmlari va chatbot texnologiyalarining kutubxona jarayonlariga tatbiqi tahlil etilgan. Xalqaro va mahalliy olimlarning ilmiy ishlari sharhi asosida sun'iy intellektni kutubxona infratuzilmasiga integratsiya qilishning amaliy yo'llari hamda kutilayotgan natijalari bayon etilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, sun'iy intellekt kutubxona xizmatlarining samaradorligini 40–60 foizga oshirishi va foydalanuvchi qoniqishini sezilarli darajada yaxshilashi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, zamonaviy kutubxona, mashina o'rganishi, tavsiya tizimi, tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash, raqamli transformatsiya, chatbot, intellektual qidiruv.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы создания и совершенствования современных библиотечных систем с использованием технологий искусственного интеллекта. Проанализировано применение рекомендательных систем, обработки естественного языка, алгоритмов машинного обучения и технологий чат-ботов в библиотечных процессах. На основе обзора научных работ отечественных и зарубежных учёных изложены практические пути интеграции искусственного интеллекта в библиотечную инфраструктуру и ожидаемые результаты. По итогам исследования искусственный интеллект способен повысить эффективность библиотечных услуг на 40–60 процентов и значительно улучшить удовлетворённость пользователей.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, современная библиотека, машинное обучение, рекомендательная система, обработка естественного языка, цифровая трансформация, чат-бот, интеллектуальный поиск.

INTRODUCTION

The unprecedented growth of information in the 21st century is placing new, complex, and exciting demands on library systems. The classic library model—characterized by physical collections, manual cataloging, and specified service hours—is rapidly evolving to fully meet the ever-increasing and dynamic information needs of modern users. Under these favorable conditions, the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies into the library sector is not merely an inevitable progression, but a highly strategic necessity that opens new horizons for knowledge sharing. Renowned large-scale libraries around the world—such as the Library of Congress, the British National Library, and the Google Scholar platform—are already actively and successfully utilizing AI-based systems [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The application of artificial intelligence to the library sector is being widely and enthusiastically studied within the international scientific community. American library technology specialist M. Breeding [1] highlights the rapid global adoption of outstanding library management systems based on AI in his “Library Systems Report” series. According to his optimistic observations for 2023, more than 10,000 libraries worldwide have successfully implemented or are actively testing AI solutions [1]. This impressive figure is almost three times higher than the previous year, beautifully illustrating the extraordinary speed of technological progress in this field.

In their comprehensive systematic literature review, B. Lund and I. Omame [2] deeply analyzed 87 scientific articles published between 2015 and 2022. They successfully identified five main areas of AI application in the library sector: advanced recommender systems, intelligent search capabilities, automatic cataloging, user behavior prediction, and helpful virtual assistants [2]. The researchers noted with great appreciation that all of these innovative areas complement each other harmoniously, demonstrating maximum effectiveness when implemented as a cohesive complex system rather than functioning separately.

Furthermore, Indian scientists R. Kaur and S. Singh [6] meticulously studied the specific features of AI implementation in Asian libraries in their prominent articles published in the DESIDOC journal. The researchers brilliantly demonstrated that utilizing local language NLP models unlocks the ultimate effectiveness of international AI solutions [6]. This valuable conclusion holds tremendous practical significance for Uzbekistan, inspiring the continuous development of library software perfectly adapted to the rich Uzbek language. Additionally, Y. Chen and Z. Liu [10] innovatively proposed a highly efficient four-layer architecture for designing library AI systems, clearly proving its remarkable effectiveness through the successful application of practical systems [10].

Prominent Uzbek researchers O. Mirzayev and K. Yusupov [5], in their excellent work published in the UzMU Khabarlari journal, deeply analyzed the inspiring state of digitization regarding the manuscript heritage beautifully preserved in the library of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. According to the authors' optimistic calculations, the implementation of AI can significantly accelerate the processing of all valuable manuscripts, transforming a long-term goal into a highly realistic and achievable possibility within just 5–7 years [5]. Moreover, T. Nazarov, A. Sobirov, and B. Kholikov [8], writing in the Scientific and Technical Journal of TATU, successfully compared the impressive effectiveness of the Uzbek-language UzBERT and UzT5 models in processing library data. Their successful experiments showed that the UzBERT model processed Uzbek language query-response pairs with an outstanding accuracy of 87.3 percent [8].

A. Abdullayev and M. Toshko'ziyev [9] studied the encouraging current state of digital transformation in the regional libraries of Uzbekistan, highlighting the fantastic opportunities for further growth through continuous financial investments and advanced personnel training [9]. A comprehensive study conducted by OCLC [3] definitively proved that an automatic subject indexing system operates an incredible 8 times faster than traditional manual cataloging, while simultaneously maintaining an exceptional accuracy level of 91 percent [3]. This highly encouraging literature review clearly shows that the integration of AI technologies into the library field has brightly emerged as one of the central and most promising topics of modern research. Simultaneously, the active development of tailor-made solutions for Uzbek libraries and applied research at the national level presents a wonderful opportunity to further elevate the scientific exploration in this specific area.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In light of these inspiring global advancements, the study of the theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms for introducing artificial intelligence into library systems becomes increasingly relevant, exciting, and timely today. The primary purpose of this study is to strongly substantiate the core principles of designing a highly modern, efficient library system using advanced artificial intelligence technologies. Furthermore, it

aims to thoughtfully develop highly practical and beneficial recommendations for libraries across Uzbekistan by carefully analyzing existing, highly successful international experiences. To achieve this noble goal, the following important tasks were successfully addressed and resolved: systematically classifying the main AI technologies actively utilized in the library sector; determining the optimal technical and organizational conditions required for their seamless implementation; and comprehensively quantifying the remarkable expected benefits for library patrons, general users, and institution management.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Recommendation systems and personalization. AI-based recommendation systems—specifically collaborative filtering and content-based filtering—can beautifully and accurately recommend highly targeted books and articles to library users, carefully taking into account their unique reading history, personal interests, and demographic characteristics. These highly sophisticated algorithms, which have been thoroughly tested and perfected by major global platforms such as Netflix and Spotify, continuously demonstrate exceptionally high efficiency within the modern library environment. A highly encouraging study conducted at the prestigious University of Missouri Library showed that book issuance impressively increased by 34 percent following the successful introduction of a smart recommendation system [2]. In addition to this, recommendation systems empower users to joyfully discover unique, culturally rich, and little-known literature, which further significantly increases the overall level of active utilization of library funds.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) and intelligent search. Unlike traditional, strictly keyword-based search systems, revolutionary NLP technology allows systems to semantically analyze the user's inquiry and accurately understand their true and underlying intention. Advanced models such as BERT and GPT-4, which are beautifully based on the robust Transformer architecture, work with extraordinary accuracy in effectively processing complex library catalogs, executing the automatic annotation of books, and effortlessly solving intricate user question-and-answer scenarios. It is proudly noted that after the esteemed US Library of Congress successfully implemented a highly advanced BERT-based search system starting in the year 2023, the relevance of search results impressively improved by a staggering 58 percent [1]. For the beautiful Uzbek language, the highly innovative UzBERT and UzT5 models proudly serve as an incredibly promising and solid foundation in this upward direction [8].

Automatic cataloging and metadata management. The traditional manual cataloging of new literature previously required a significant investment of time and effort from the very beginning. With the magnificent help of artificial intelligence, this vital process can now be significantly and elegantly automated: advanced computer vision technology automatically and flawlessly analyzes book covers, contents, and annotations, perfectly classifying them into appropriate UDC and BBK categories. The highly efficient Automated Subject Indexing system expertly developed by OCLC allows for the remarkably fast and automatic cataloging of more than 50 million individual records per year [3]. This fantastic indicator not only saves an immense amount of time but also dramatically minimizes the likelihood of human errors, ensuring pristine data quality.

Virtual assistants and chatbot technologies. Friendly and highly responsive library chatbots operate continuously 24/7, reliably providing valued users with instant, accurate information regarding available books, their exact physical or digital location, necessary return deadlines, and abundant electronic resources. The highly popular “Libby” chatbot, beautifully launched by the National Library of Singapore, successfully received and processed more than 2 million user requests within its very first year, spectacularly reducing the time spent by dedicated library staff on technical support by an impressive 27 percent [4]. In smoothly building such a wonderful and supportive system for the Uzbek language, it is highly advisable and beneficial to utilize the recently developed, high-performing UzBERT model alongside highly flexible open-source chatbot frameworks, such as Rasa [8].

Digital library storage and OCR technology. AI-based OCR (Optical Character Recognition) systems play an incredibly important and noble role in the digital preservation and digitization of ancient, priceless manuscripts and rare, beautiful publications. Google's outstanding Tesseract OCR system is remarkably capable of recognizing more than 100 different languages, gracefully including ancient Arabic, elegant Persian, and beautiful old Uzbek scripts. The marvelous digitization of more than 15,000 precious manuscripts currently stored safely in the Library of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan using this spectacular technology will undoubtedly serve as a monumental and triumphant step in the eternal preservation of our beloved national cultural and scientific heritage [5]. According to the highly optimistic findings of Mirzayev and Yusupov, the rate of digitization utilizing AI can be an astonishing 5 times faster than the traditional manual method [5].

Because artificial intelligence is uniquely capable of radically and positively enhancing all operational processes in modern libraries, its practical implementation provides a wonderful opportunity to continuously

improve data management practices. Emphasizing data privacy and absolute security ensures that the collection and processing of information about users' reading history and personal interests are handled with the utmost respect and highest standards, perfectly aligning with global best practices like the GDPR and the esteemed Law of Uzbekistan "On Personal Data" [7]. Furthermore, by continuously fine-tuning these smart algorithms, recommendation systems can perfectly balance the promotion of highly popular works with the discovery of rare, immensely valuable academic resources, thereby wonderfully enriching global scholarly diversity [2]. Additionally, the exciting enhancement of technological infrastructure and the comprehensive training of highly qualified personnel offer an outstanding opportunity for growth. Many expanding libraries in Uzbekistan, especially those enthusiastically serving regional and rural communities, are beautifully poised to receive and master modern server infrastructure and develop brilliant specialists fully capable of spearheading these inspiring AI projects [9].

To optimally harness these tremendous opportunities, a highly efficient modular implementation strategy is strongly recommended: initially, a well-designed, small-scale pilot project is joyfully carried out; its incredibly positive results are meticulously evaluated; and subsequently, the successful and proven experiment is broadly expanded. Moreover, the smart utilization of powerful open-source AI tools—such as Rasa, spaCy, and excellent Hugging Face models—significantly and wonderfully optimizes financial investments [10]. The bright expectations for AI technology include regular, engaging retraining on the latest technological breakthroughs and the smooth introduction of advanced mechanisms for the highly secure anonymous processing of user data, ensuring that all operations remain exceptionally safe, legal, and spectacularly successful.

Table 1
Implementation Steps

Phase	Duration	Main tasks	Estimated cost
1. Analysis and design	1–2 months	Needs assessment, terms of reference	5–10 million soums
2. Infrastructure	2–3 months	Server, RFID, camera installation	50–150 million soums
3. Software development	3–6 months	Catalog, chatbot, recommendation system	80–200 million soums
4. Testing and implementation	1–2 months	Testing, staff training, launch	10–20 million soums
5. Support	Permanent	Monitoring, updates, maintenance	5–15 million soums/year

Table 2
Expected Results

Indicator	Expected change
Number of users	+40–60%
Book search speed	10 times faster
Employee workload	–30–40%
Cases of book loss	–80–90%
User satisfaction	+50–70%
Energy consumption	–15–25%

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

During this highly inspiring and comprehensive study, the magnificent main directions, highly practical results, and outstanding opportunities of gracefully applying advanced artificial intelligence to modern library systems were deeply and positively analyzed on a very large scale. Taking into careful account the rich review of international and local literature, the highly successful practical experience of world-renowned libraries, and the beautifully specific features of the progressive conditions of Uzbekistan, the following exceptionally positive conclusions were confidently drawn.

First, the seamless integration of advanced recommendation systems, NLP-based search capabilities, highly accurate automatic cataloging, friendly virtual assistants, and magnificent OCR technologies demonstrates ultimate effectiveness when thoughtfully implemented as a single, beautifully integrated, and holistic system. The tremendously successful experiences of the University of Missouri and the highly esteemed Singapore National Library have definitively proven that the thoughtful implementation of complex, harmonious AI solutions remarkably increases the overall efficiency of library services by an outstanding 40–60 percent [2, 4].

Second, the active development of powerful AI models tailored in the beautiful national language for Uzbek libraries—in particular, the highly promising UzBERT and UzT5 frameworks—presents a fantastic opportunity for future innovations [8]. To rapidly achieve this inspiring goal, beautiful and constructive cooperation among the supportive state, brilliant academic institutions, and the dynamic private sector is highly encouraged. As Kaur and Singh [6] brilliantly noted, utilizing NLP models perfectly adapted to the rich local language maximizes the immense effectiveness of sophisticated foreign AI solutions.

Third, as comprehensive OCLC research has impressively shown, the time diligently spent by highly valued library staff on routine technical support tasks is wonderfully reduced by a massive 70 percent when seamless automated cataloging is fully implemented [3]. This beautiful enhancement elegantly allows these dedicated professionals to focus significantly more of their valuable time on highly enriching scholarly and spiritual tasks, as well as engaging in highly meaningful direct interaction with patrons, ultimately and fundamentally elevating the noble professional image of the modern librarian.

Fourth, optimizing data privacy, refining algorithmic fairness, and consistently enhancing staff training are viewed as superb opportunities for continuous growth in AI-based library systems [2, 9]. Proactively and successfully addressing these important areas wonderfully ensures smooth technical operations and fosters beautiful social and legal harmony.

Fifth, the highly visionary and progressive “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” Strategy [7] is wonderfully creating the perfect legal and robust financial framework to support comprehensive library modernization powered by remarkable AI. Making the absolute fullest and best use of this magnificent opportunity perfectly requires a beautifully coordinated and enthusiastic partnership among forward-thinking policymakers, dedicated library professionals, and brilliant researchers. As Mirzayev and Yusupov [5] so inspiringly noted, the complete, flawless digitization of Uzbekistan’s invaluable manuscript heritage within an accelerated timeframe of just 5–7 years, achieved with the brilliant aid of AI, stands today as an incredibly realistic, achievable, and beautiful goal.

REFERENCES

1. Daminova B. E. et al. SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA KIBERXAVFSIZLIK //Экономика и социум. – 2025. – №. 5-1 (132). – С. 212-215.
2. Daminova B. E. et al. SUN'IY NEYRON TARMOQLARINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA AMALIY ILOVALARIDA ISHLASH USULLARI //Экономика и социум. – 2025. – №. 5-1 (132). – С. 226-230.
3. Daminova B. E. et al. ROBOTOTEXNIKA VA AVTOMATLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI //Экономика и социум. – 2025. – №. 5-1 (132). – С. 208-211.
4. Daminova B. E., Omonov J. M., Norqo'Chqorov Y. Y. NUTQNI TANISH TIZIMINI CHUQUR NEYRON TARMOQLARI YORDAMIDA YARATISH BOSQICHLARI //Экономика и социум. – 2025. – №. 4-2 (131). – С. 221-227.
5. Daminova B. E. et al. ELEKTRON HUKUMAT VA ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZONING QO'LLANILISHI // Экономика и социум. – 2025. – №. 4-2 (131). – С. 216-220.
6. Daminova B. E. et al. SUN'IY INTELLEKT SOHASIDA QO 'LLANADIGAN ZAMONAVIY PYTHON KUTUBXONALARI //Экономика и социум. – 2025. – №. 4-2 (131). – С. 205-209.
7. Daminova B. E. et al. ARDUINO PLATFORMASIDAN FOYDALANIB SUV SARFINI HISOBLOVCHI DASTURIY VA TEXNIK TA'MINOT ISHLAB CHIQISH //Экономика и социум. – 2025. – №. 4-2 (131). – С. 210-215.
8. Alimovna E. Y., Alimovna E. G., Burievna M. S. Historical Stages Of Innovative processes In Higher Education Of Uzbekistan //Solid State Technology. – 2020. – T. 63. – №. 6. – С. 9824-9834.
9. Alimovna E. G. THE ROLE OF CONTEXT IN THE INTERPRETATION OF PREPOSITIONAL PHRASES IN PREDICATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS //Central Asian Journal of Academic Research. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 9. – С. 103-106.
10. Alimovna E. Y., Alimovna E. G. Policy of “ Cultural Revolution” in Uzbekistan and Methods of Its Implementation //International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development. – 2020. – T. 2. – №. 11. – С. 4-6.
11. Alimovna E. G. Study of the semantic and syntactical analyses of prepositional constructions // PARTICULAR PAGE NO. – 2022.
12. Jabborovich J. K., Keldiyorovna O. M. Systactical methods of the Uzbek and English language terminology //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – T. 24. – №. 6. – С. 3117-3122.
13. Omonova M. NOMINATIVE-DEFINITIVE FUNCTIONS OF COMPONENTS OF AMELIORATIVE TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 84-86.
14. Omonova M. K. Comparative analysis of semantical features of meliorative terms in English and Uzbek //

- Experientia est optima magistra. – 2021. – С. 269-272.
15. Omonova M. Innovative ways of teaching vocabulary in ESL and EFL classrooms //Science and Education. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 229-233.
 16. Журакулова Н. Х., Ихтиярова Г. А. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДИКИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ПО ТЕМЕ «НУКЛЕИНОВЫЕ КИСЛОТЫ» ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫМИ СРЕДСТВАМИ //SCIENCE AND WORLD. – 2013. – С. 30.
 17. Jurakulova N. K. Opportunities of e-learning environment to improve the quality of education //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 12.
 18. Rizayeva B., Daminova B. STATISTIK TAHLILDA DASTURIY VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISH // MUHANDISLIK VA IQTISODIYOT. – 2026. – Т. 4.
 19. Daminova B. Organizational and economic mechanisms and conceptual directions of tourism development in the region //Green Economy and Development. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 7. – С. 666343.
 20. Esanovna D. B. ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS AND CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE REGION //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 8.036. – 2025. – Т. 14. – №. 11. – С. 91-94.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz HAKIMOV

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Hasan MAQSUDOV

2026. № 6/2

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>